

Quantum Momentum, Wavelength, Impulse and Special Relativity?

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The concept of impulse exists in Newtonian mechanics, but wavelength is not associated with momentum in such a case. Even for light (which has a wavelength) reflection from a stationary mirror or refraction into a stationary medium, the idea of momentum without wavelength may be applied (1). In quantum mechanics, however, momentum is directly linked to wavelength through $p = \hbar / \text{wavelength}$, but what does this relationship mean for interactions? Wave mechanics were known long before quantum mechanics and special relativity and often involve following two wavefronts as they interact to see if their spacing remains the same. The interaction itself, however, seems to be very much like a Newtonian impulse one. Thus there are two types of “mechanics” occurring, one linked to impulse and the other to wave features i.e. delays which disrupt the spacing of wave fronts.

In particular we try to associate this idea with the reflection of light from a moving mirror. In (2) the author considers such a scenario with two wavefronts, each undergoing identical impulse-like interactions, but calculates how the movement of the mirror during the time the two wavefronts react affects the distance between the two reflected wavefronts. The author argues that this approach allows one to obtain the same results as special relativity. In this note we argue that such an analysis may give insight to quantum mechanical interactions i.e. help clarify how momentum and wavelength are linked in a practical problem. As a result, we argue that quantum mechanics of a free particle and special relativity are closely linked and that quantum mechanics like wavefront mechanics combines Newtonian interactions with an uncertainty in the particle position i.e. two extreme points separated by a wavelength.

Impulse

Newtonian mechanics introduced the idea of impulse hits. Indeed, Newton viewed light as a particle and experiments with impulse hits on foil seem to be consistent with this idea. Furthermore reflection and refraction may be described in terms of momentum (see (1)) without any notion of wavelength being introduced. It is also known, however, that light exhibits wave behaviour and that $p = \hbar / \text{wavelength}$ (also for a quantum free particle). How does one associate the concept of wavelength with momentum in a practical problem?

Wavefronts

Wavefront mechanics has been studied long before special relativity and quantum mechanics. One considers two fronts separated by a wavelength and analyses how each interacts in an impulse manner. One then considers the two reflected wavefronts to see if the same wavelength is maintained. This approach seems to make use of two types of mechanics. First there is the usual Newtonian mechanics linked to impulses, but then there is the idea of a wavelength so that even though the impulses associated with each wavefront are in principle the same, the system may have changed during the time interval during which the second wavefront interacts (e.g. in the case of a moving mirror). We argue that this seems to be a kind

of quantum mechanical scenario. There is uncertainty of finding the quantum particle within a wavelength so one cannot simply treat it as a point as in Newtonian mechanics. Wherever it is, however, within the wavelength, it has a momentum p . The two wavefront approach seems to account for two extreme positions of the particle and one is forced to apply a Newtonian impulse approach to both and then find the relationship between the two results after the interaction.

Moving Mirror From (2)

We briefly outline the ideas from (2). Consider a ray of light making an angle of AA with the x axis and a mirror on the y axis moving with velocity v in the x direction (to the right). Consider two points on the ray A and B (with A to the left of B) with the two separated by an initial wavelength w_0 . Let B (the first wavefront) reflect from the mirror at time t_0 at point B' on the ray. The reflected first wavefront will move at an angle BB relative to the x axis to point B' arriving at t_0 . The distance traveled is $c(t-t_0)$. A , the second wavefront, moves along the ray until it hits the moving mirror and reflects in exactly the same way. The perpendicular distance between the two reflected wavefronts in the reflected wavelength w which is not the same as w_0 .

Consider A' as the point at which the second wavefront hits the mirror. Then:

$$BA' \cos(AA) = v(t-t_0) \quad ((1))$$

Next the distance from A' to a line from B to the reflected second wavefront ray and perpendicular to it is given by $BA' \cos(AA + BB)$. Thus:

$$W = c(t-t_0) + v(t-t_0)\cos(AA+BB) / \cos(AA) \quad ((2))$$

From this the author of (2) obtains an expression for w/w_0 in terms of v , c and $\cos(AA)$. We leave the details to (2), but wish to point out three main features. First the speed of light v is always the same as mentioned in (2). Secondly, two wavefronts are required in the analysis and thirdly, the exact same impulse reaction occurs for each wavefront i.e. a Newtonian impulse type of result. The wavefront analysis combines the notion of a wavelength together with Newtonian impulses. We argue that this is a quantum mechanical approach. The two wavefronts demonstrate that one does not really know where the particle (light) is, but there is a regular delineation of space into wavelength portions. Thus even though the particle has a fixed $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ at any point, the two extreme points of the wavelength must be considered using Newtonian mechanics. In static problems such as reflection or refraction from stationary objects one does not need to worry so much about the two wavefronts. Thus $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ is simply a math relationship. We argue, however, that there must be a physical meaning to the wavelength interval even though there is only one fixed momentum value. We take the two wavefront analysis as being this description with each having the same impulse interaction. If there is motion in the system (such as a moving mirror) during the time that the two wavefronts interact, this may affect the final spacing between the two post-interaction wavefronts even though each underwent the same impulse reaction at the moving mirror surface.

A simpler way to see this is to consider a ray of light moving along the x axis hitting a moving mirror. Again one has points A and B (A to the left of B) separated by w_0 (initial wavelength). Both wavefront rays reflect and move to the left on the x axis., but:

$W_0 + v(t) = ct$ (B reflects at $x=0$ at $t=0$) for the second wavefront which reflects at $t=t$ ((3))

The first wavefront is ct to the left of $x=0$ at t . The second wavefront is at: vt to the right of $x=0$ because this is the distance the mirror has moved to the right of $x=0$ from $t=0$. Thus the separation of the two i.e. w the new reflected wavelength is:

$$W = ct + vt = cw_0/(c-v) + vw_0/(c-v) \quad \text{or} \quad w/w_0 = (c+v)/(c-v) \quad ((4))$$

Again two wavefronts must be used in the analysis because the mirror is moving, but each undergoes the same impulse hit.

Special Relativity

So far no mention has been made of special relativity. The two ideas implemented are the notion of a Newtonian impulse and two wavefronts because one has a wavelength and uncertainty in the position of the particle or light. (2), however, argues that the wavefront approach produces the same results as special relativity and allows one to obtain a result for a moving mirror without using Lorentz transforms. We argue that the wavefront approach is equivalent to the ideas of quantum mechanics for a free particle or light. Thus we conclude that free particle quantum mechanics is directly linked to special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, quantum mechanics uses the relationship $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$, but one often thinks of p in terms of Newtonian impulse hits. For example, for the reflection of light from a stationary surface or refraction, one may think in terms of momentum and impulse hits. $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ becomes a recipe for linking two numbers p and wavelength, but we argue that there should be physical relevance to the wavelength. The relevance usually given is that the wavelength defines resolution. We argue that the moving mirror problem seems to give a physical example of p and wavelength combined in a quantum object i.e. a photon. The momentum is associated with Newtonian type impulse hits, but from quantum mechanics the particle/light is somewhere within the wavelength. Thus one has to consider two extreme points on the wavelength (i.e. two wavefronts) and examine how each interacts with, for example, a moving mirror. During the interval time between the two wavefront interactions the mirror moves. Thus even though the impulse interactions of the two wavefronts are identical the separation of the two reflected wavefronts is affected. Thus both the idea of wavelength and momentum together are needed to solve a moving mirror problem, while such is not the case for a stationary mirror. We argue that this demonstrates the quantum features of the problem. At the same time, one may perform a Lorentz transformation to “make” the mirror stationary, solve the

stationary problem and perform an opposite Lorentz transformation to move back to the lab. Thus we argue that the quantum mechanics of a free particle is closely linked to special relativity.

References

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2. Gjrhcinovskci, A. The Doppler Effect from a Uniformly Moving Mirror (2004 or later)
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